

Timeline for the ILC experiments

2021 IDT calls for EoI

Necessary R&D for EoI

2022 ----- Assumed start of Pre-lab -----

2022 EoI presentation

Necessary R&D for LoI

2023 **LoI submission and presentation**

Continuation of R&D

Selection process by the ILCC

2024 **ILCC recommendation on the first set of the projects to proceed toward TP**

Necessary R&D for TP

2025 TP submission and presentation of the first set of experiments

Continuation of R&D

Selection process by the ILCC

2026 ----- Assumed start of ILC-lab -----

2026-27 ILCC recommendation for the first set of experiments to proceed toward TDRs

2027 **ILC-lab approval of the first set of experiments and request to proceed toward TDRs**

- Funding agencies will not provide dedicated ILC detector R&D funds before the Pre-lab being established.
- For some EoIs, R&D would be needed to make LoIs.
→ driving the timing for the LoI submission
- Selection process starts with the LoIs.
→ driving the timing for the LoI decision
- Experiments are formally approved based on TPs.
- The ILC-lab is needed for approvals.
- Availability of resources is part of the approval criteria.
→ driving the timing for the TP decision
- These considerations are for the initial set of experiments. There could be more experiments proposed at later time.